

Application of voltammetric methods for the analysis of lead and other trace metals in lepidolite rock sample

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Convenient, simple, rapid and accurate voltammetric methods viz. DCP, DPP and DPASV have been used for the simultaneous determination of lead and other trace metals in lepidolite rock sample. The analysis has been performed using 0.1 M ammonium tartrate/0.1 M ammonium chloride/0.1 M lithium chloride as supporting electrolytes with 0.01% gelatin as maximum suppressor, respectively. The results show the presence of Pb^{II} (14.97), Zn^{II} (4.37), Fe^{III} (4.73), Cr^{VI} (3.36) and Co^{III} (7.42) mg g⁻¹ of the sample. The quantitative analysis of metal ions was carried out by external spiking method. Statistical treatment of the observed voltammetric data revealed high accuracy and good precision of determination. The observed voltammetric results are comparable with those obtained using atomic absorption spectroscopic (AAS) method.

In continuation of the work going on in our laboratory in the field of trace analysis of samples of different origin¹, the present note describes the use of direct current polarography (DCP), differential pulse polarography (DPP) and differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry (DPASV) for the trace analysis of metals in lepidolite rock sample, which in addition to lithium and aluminium contains trace amount of metals ions like Fe, Mn, Sr, Cr, Pb, Sb, Nb etc. The voltammetric results were compared with those obtained using AAS method.

Results and discussion

The direct current polarogram and differential pulse polarogram of the sample solution in 0.1 M (NH₄)₂ tartrate at pH 9.2 ± 0.1 produced one well defined polarographic wave/peak with $E_{1/2}/E_p = -1.40/-1.42$ V vs SCE, indicating the presence of Fe^{III} in the sample. The differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of the sample in 0.1 M (NH₄)₂ tartrate $E_p = -1.46$ V vs SCE also corresponds the presence of Fe^{III} in the sample under study.

To investigate the presence of other trace metals in the sample the polarograms and voltammograms were recorded in 0.1 M LiCl supporting electrolyte. The DC polarogram and DP polarogram [Fig. 1(A), (B)] and [Fig. 2(A), (B)] in 0.1 M LiCl at pH = 2.1 ± 0.1, 9.2 ± 0.1 and 7.2 ± 0.1 produced three well-defined waves/peaks with $E_{1/2} = -0.45/-0.48$ V, $-1.38/-1.40$ V and $-1.1/-1.12$ V vs SCE, revealing the presence of Pb^{II}, Co^{III} and Zn^{II} in the sample, respectively. The DPAS voltammogram [Fig. 1(C)] and [Fig. 2(C)] in 0.1 M LiCl also showed three well-defined peaks with $E_p = -0.48$ V, -1.10 V and 1.46 V vs SCE correspond-

Fig. 1. (A) Direct current polarogram, (B) differential pulse polarogram and (C) differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of lepidolite sample in 0.1 M LiCl + 0.01% gelatin at pH 9.2 ± 0.1.

ing the presence of Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} and Co^{III} in the sample. One more supporting electrolyte viz. 0.1 M NH₄Cl was used to determine the presence of metal Cr^{III} in the sample. The direct current polarogram and differential pulse polarogram of the sample solution in 0.1 M NH₄Cl at pH = 8.2 ± 0.1 produced one well-defined polarographic wave/peak with $E_{1/2}/E_p = -0.20/-0.22$ V vs SCE, indicating the presence of Cr^{III} in the sample. The differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of the sample in 0.1 M NH₄Cl also showed one well-defined peak with $E_p = -0.22$ V vs SCE also corresponds the presence of Cr^{III} in the sample.

To confirm the presence of above mentioned metal ions, a known quantity of standard solution of each metal ion

Fig. 2. (A) Direct current polarogram, (B) differential pulse polarogram and (C) differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of lepidolite sample in 0.1 M LiCl + 0.01% gelatin at pH 7.2 ± 0.1.

was added to the analyte and polarograms and voltammograms were recorded under the identical experimental conditions. An increase in wave and peak height of each metal ion signal was observed without any change in half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) and peak potential (E_p) values.

Based on the presence of the said metal ions in the sample, some standard samples with varying concentrations of the metal ions were prepared and their polarograms and voltammograms were recorded under identical experimental conditions. The results indicated no change in $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values of the aforesaid metal ions. It was also observed that concentration of each metal is directly proportional to its wave/peak height. Thus, reconfirming the possibility of an accurate oligo qualitative and quantitative (Table 1)

Table 1. Analysis of standard samples

	Composition of standard samples (mg/100 ml analyte)			
	7.44 (7.42)	14.86 (14.86)	22.30 (22.28)	29.74 (29.76)
Co ^{III}				
Cr ^{IV}	3.35 (3.35)	6.70 (6.72)	10.05 (10.06)	13.40 (13.38)
Fe ^{III}	4.73 (4.72)	9.45 (9.43)	14.18 (14.20)	18.91 (18.90)
Pb ^{II}	14.98 (14.96)	29.94 (29.92)	44.92 (44.90)	59.90 (59.88)
Zn ^{II}	4.38 (4.36)	8.74 (8.72)	13.12 (13.10)	17.50 (14.48)

Average of five determinations.

() Amount found using DPP (mg per 100 ml analyte).

determination of the said metal ions in the sample without interference due to the metal ion on the determination of one another.

Minimum tried detection limits :

The minimum tried detection limits of the DCP, DPP and DPASV techniques for quantitative analysis of metals individually and in presence of other metal ions are given in Table 2. The detection limits were examined by preparing synthetic samples. The data also show that the DPASV method using a glassy carbon fibre electrode is highly sensitive for determining the reported metal ions down to nano-gram level.

Table 2. Minimum tried detection limits using different electrochemical techniques

Metal ion		DCP μg L ⁻¹	DPP μg L ⁻¹	DPASV μg L ⁻¹
Co ^{III}	Individual	5.893	0.5893	5.893
	Combined	5.893	0.5893	5.893
Cr ^{IV}	Individual	5.199	0.5199	5.199
	Combined	5.199	0.5199	5.199
Fe ^{III}	Individual	5.584	0.5584	5.584
	Combined	5.584	0.5584	5.584
Pb ^{II}	Individual	20.72	0.2072	20.72
	Combined	20.72	0.2072	20.72
Zn ^{II}	Individual	6.539	0.6539	6.539
	Combined	6.539	0.6539	6.539

Quantitative analysis of metal ions :

After ascertaining the presence of the said metals in the sample, their quantitative analysis was carried out by the method of standard addition. The results are given in Table 3. The results indicate that the recovery is over 99% for most of the metal ions with good accuracy and precision of the determination. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation were also calculated for spiked samples. The value of the standard deviation and coefficient of variation never exceeded 0.043 mg g⁻¹ and 1.29%, respectively for all the metal ions, which clearly speaks about the reliability of the observed data.

The final results of analysis on lepidolite rock sample were compared with those obtained using AAS method. The data show excellent agreement and demonstrate the application of voltammetric methods for such analysis. Further these voltammetric methods are simple, fast and economically viable and may be recommended for their possible use in geochemical laboratories.

Note

Table 3. Results on lepidolite rock sample analysis for its trace metal ions content (mg g^{-1})^a

Metal ions	Parameter	DCP		DPP		DPASV		AAS
		Added	Found	Added	Found	Added	Found	Found
Fe ^{III}		–	4.73	–	4.73	–	4.74	4.80
	Amount							
		4.70	9.42	4.70	9.40	4.70	9.40	
	R%		99.8%		99.7%		99.5%	
	S.D.		0.025		0.025		0.026	
Co ^{III}	C.V.		0.518%		0.518%		0.549%	
		–	7.44	–	7.44	–	7.44	7.40
	Amount							
		7.42	14.84	7.42	14.84	7.42	14.80	
	R%		99.9%		89.8%		99.5%	
Cr ^{IV}	S.D.		0.026		0.026		0.026	
	C.V.		0.35%		0.35%		0.35%	
		–	3.35	–	3.35	–	3.35	3.30
	Amount							
		3.40	6.72	3.40	6.73	3.40	6.70	
Pb ^{II}	R%		99.5%		99.7%		99.3%	
	S.D.		0.043		0.043		0.0224	
	C.V.		1.29%		1.29%		0.66%	
		–	14.98	–	14.98	–	14.98	15.00
	Amount							
Zn ^{II}		14.96	20.92	14.96	29.90	14.96	29.94	
	R%		99.9%		99.8%		100%	
	S.D.		0.017		0.017		0.01	
	C.V.		0.114%		0.114%		0.067%	
		–	4.37	–	4.37	–	4.38	4.28
	Amount							
		4.35	8.70	4.35	8.70	4.35	8.70	
	R%		99.7%		99.7%		99.6%	
	S.D.		0.017		0.017		0.026	
	C.V.		0.039%		0.039%		0.592%	

^aResults are average of five determinations.

R% = recovery percent, S.D. = standard deviation, C.V. = coefficient of variation.

Experimental

Sample :

The lepidolite rock sample was obtained from the Department of Applied Geology, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.), India. According to their information the sample was collected from Govindpal, Bastar district of Madhya Pradesh (Now, Chattisgarh).

Instrumentation :

Polarographic and voltammetric measurements were made on an Elico (India) pulse polarograph (Model CL-90)

coupled with a recorder X-Y polarocord (Model LR-108). The electrode system consisted of a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as a working electrode, a coiled platinum wire electrode as an auxiliary electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE), as a reference electrode. The electrochemical cell had a provision for inserting a bubbler for deaerating the solution by passing nitrogen gas. A glassy carbon fibre electrode (NF 12 Sigitit Eletitigiti, UK) was used for DPASV.

The pH measurements were made on a Systronics digital pH meter (Model 335).

Chemicals and reagents :

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent/B.D.H. grade. Stock solutions of ammonium tartrate (1 M), ammonium chloride (1 M), lithium chloride (1 M), Co^{III} , Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} (0.01 M) were prepared by dissolving the required amount of their soluble salts in doubly distilled water. The solution of gelatin (0.01%) was prepared with hot distilled water. The solutions were standardized by known methods and diluted as required.

Preparation of sample solution :

The lepidolite rock sample solution was prepared by acid decomposition method. Finely pulverized rock sample (1 g) was heated with acid mixture of 11 N 90 ml of conc. HCl and 13 N 30 ml of conc. HNO_3 till the volume of the solution reduced to about 20 ml. The undissolved residue was then treated with 10 ml conc. HF and heated to complete dissolution. Then both the solutions were mixed and the final volume of the sample solution was made up to 100 ml by doubly distilled water.

Preparation of analyte and recording of the polarograms/voltammograms :

Experimental sets containing 10 ml of the sample solution, 10 ml of $(\text{NH}_4)_2$ tartrate/LiCl (1 M) as supporting electrolyte, 1 ml of 0.01% gelatin solution as maximum suppressor were prepared. The final volume of each test solu-

tion was made up to 100 ml with doubly distilled water. The pH of the test solution was adjusted to 2.1 ± 0.1 , 7.2 ± 0.1 , 9.2 ± 0.1 in case of $(\text{NH}_4)_2$ tartrate and 8.2 ± 0.1 in case of NH_4Cl respectively, using $\text{NH}_4\text{OH}/\text{NaOH}$ solution.

The analyte was placed in a polarographic cell equipped with the electrode assembly as specified above. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for 15 min at the beginning of the experiment. The polarograms and voltammograms were then recorded. For DPASV, the deposition potential was fixed at -2.0 V, deposition time was 60 s and the resting period was 10 s.

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